

Vibration Control of Arc Type Shell Using Active Constrained Layer Damping

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ABSTRACT

The Active Constrained Layer Damping (ACLD) combines the simplicity and reliability of passive damping with the low weight and high efficiency of active control to attain high damping characteristics. The proposed ACLD treatment consists of a viscoelastic damping which is sandwiched between an active piezoelectric layer and a host structure. In this manner, the smart ACLD consists of a Passive Constrained Layer Damping (PCLD) which is augmented with an active control in response to the structural vibrations. The Arc type shell model is introduced to describe the interactions between the vibrating host structure, piezoelectric actuator and viscoelastic damping. The system is modeled by applying ARMAX (AutoRegressive Moving Average Vector) model and converted into a state-space form in order to design control law. The performance of ACLD system is determined and compared with PCLD in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of the ACLD treatment.

Keywords : Active Constrained Layer Damping(ACLD) , Passive Constrained Layer Damping (PCLD) , AutoRegressive Moving Average Vector(ARMAX) , Vibration Control , Piezoelectric material.

1. INTRODUCTION

Passive surface treatments have been extensively utilized, as a simple and reliable means, for the vibration damping of plain and sandwiched structures. However, these passive surface treatments have limitations to their practical use due to adding considerable weight to the vibrating host structures. To overcome this disadvantage of passive damping treatments, many researchers have been investigated to develop various passive and active control strategies. One of alternatives is Active Constrained Layer Damping (ACLD), which has dual functions of active and passive treatments. This method makes it possible to reduce the weight of structures as reducing the size of passive treatments and obtain the higher damping ratios over a broad frequency range due to its active control efforts.

Baz [1] developed a mathematical model of ACLD to investigate the fundamentals and underlying principles governing the operation of the ACLD treatments. Shen [2] developed another form of ACLD called Intelligent Constrained Layer (ICL) damping. Rongong, et al. [3] modeled a hybrid constrained layer/piezoceramics as sandwiching a constraining layer between a piezoceramic and a viscoelastic layer. Huang et al. [4] discussed some design considerations for pure PCLD, pure active control, and ACLD. Ray and Baz [5] developed a finite element model to describe the vibrations of a shell that was partially treated with ACLD.

In this paper, the cantilevered shell type arc that is made of carbon/epoxy composite material is chosen to investigate the potentials of ACLD effectiveness. By using system identification method, the arc/ACLD system is modeled as ARMAX (AutoRegressive Moving Average Vector) and converted into the state space form to design optimal control laws. The Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) controller is used to find optimal control gains. The attractive attributes of the ACLD approach are utilized to control, experimentally, the first bending mode of vibration of the arc/ACLD system. The ACLD is envisioned to be an effective means for augmenting the simplicity of passive damping with the low weight and high efficiency of active controls to attain high damping

characteristics. To measure the ability of vibration reduction performance for arc type shell model, experiments are performed about three type specimens of Plain, PCLD, ACLD.

2. THE CONCEPT OF ACTIVE CONSTRAINED LAYER DAMPING

The ACLD treatment consists of a conventional passive constrained layer damping which is augmented with efficient active control means to control the strain of the constraining layer, in response to the structural vibrations as shown in Figure 1. The viscoelastic damping layer is sandwiched between two piezoelectric layers. The three-layer composite ACLD when bonded to the vibrating plate acts as a SMART constraining layer damping treatment with built-in sensing and actuation capabilities.

Fig. 1 Schematic drawing of active constrained layer damping[1]

The sensing, as indicated by the sensor voltage V_s is provided by the piezoelectric layer that is directly bonded to the plate surface. The actuation is generated by the other piezoelectric layer which acts as an active constraining layer that is activated by the control voltage V_c . With appropriate strain control, through proper manipulation of V_s , the shear deformation of the viscoelastic damping layer can be increased, the energy dissipation mechanism can be enhanced and the structural vibration can be damped out. Also, the ACLD provides a practical means for controlling the vibration of massive structures with the currently available piezoelectric actuators without the need for excessively large actuation voltages. This is due to the fact that the ACLD properly utilizes the piezoelectric actuator to control the shear in the soft viscoelastic core, which is a task compatible with the low control authority capabilities of the currently available piezoelectric materials.

3. CONTROL LAW DESIGN OF ARC/ACLD SYSTEM

3.1. SYSTEM IDENTIFICATION

ARMAX model is chosen to obtain the system parameters of arc/ACLD system due to its physical similarity of the governing equations of motion. Considering the structure's vibrational modes, the equations of motion for a structure can be expressed as follows:

$$(m_c s^2 + c_c s + k_c) Y(s) = (k_a s^2 + k_v + k_p) U(s) \quad (1)$$

where m_c , c_c , k_c are modal mass, damping, stiffness matrix, respectively. The gains, k_p , k_v , k_a are for the displacement, velocity, and acceleration, respectively. $Y(s)$ and $U(s)$ are the Laplace transform of a full-state input and feedback control effort. Equation (1) can be converted into a general equation of motion for a discrete time response including disturbances for input and output as follows:

$$(a_0 q^n + a_1 q^{n-1} + \dots + a_n) y(t) = (b_0 q^n + b_1 q^{n-1} + \dots + b_n) u(t) + (c_0 + c_1 q^{n-1} + \dots + c_n) e(t) \quad (2)$$

where $y(t)$ is a vector consisting of those states that are to be measured and $u(t)$ is a input variable vector. Dividing equation (2) into forward shift operator, q_n , equation (2) becomes:

$$a_0 y(t) + a_1 y(t-1) + \dots + a_n y(t-n) = b_1 u(t-1) + \dots + b_n u(t-n) + e(t) + c_1 e(t-1) + \dots + c_n e(t-n) \quad (3)$$

Assuming that b_0 is equal to zero and that a_0 and c_0 are equal to one, the equation (3) becomes:

$$y(t) = \left[1 - \frac{A(q^{-1})}{C(q^{-1})} \right] y(t) + \frac{B(q^{-1})}{C(q^{-1})} u(t) + e(t) \quad (4)$$

where $A(q^{-1}) = 1 + a_1 q^{-1} + \dots + a_n q^{-n}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
B(q^{-1}) &= b + 1q^{-1} + \dots + c_n q^{-n}, \\
C(q^{-1}) &= 1 + c_1 q^{-1} + \dots + c_n q^{-n}, \\
\theta^T &= (a_1 \dots a_n \quad b_1 \dots b_n \quad c_1 \dots c_n).
\end{aligned}$$

Here, $e(t)$ is a error vector. Now, we define an estimated output, $\hat{y}(t)$, as follows:

$$\hat{y}(t) = \left[1 - \frac{A(q^{-1})}{C(q^{-1})} \right] y(t) + \frac{B(q^{-1})}{C(q^{-1})} u(t) \quad (5)$$

An error function between an input and estimated input signal is defined:

$$\varepsilon(t) = y(t) - \hat{y}(t) \quad (6)$$

From the equation (5) and (6), the estimated output can simply be expressed as the following form:

$$\hat{y}(t) = \hat{y}(t/\theta) = \theta^T \varphi(t) \quad (7)$$

where $\varphi(t) = (-y(t-1) \quad \dots \quad -y(t-na) \quad u(t) \quad \dots \quad u(t-nb) \quad \varepsilon(t-1) \quad \dots \quad \varepsilon(t-nc))$

The parameter, θ , can be obtained as minimization the following equation which is a function of error, $\varepsilon(t)$.

$$V(\theta) = E \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^T(t) \Lambda^{-1} \varepsilon(t) \quad (8)$$

where Λ is a weighing matrix. In order to minimize the equation (8), Stochastic Newton method can be applied:

$$\hat{\theta}(t) = \hat{\theta}(t-1) + \gamma(t) \left[V''(\hat{\theta}(t-1)) \right]^{-1} Q(\hat{\theta}(t-1)) \quad (9)$$

where $V''(\theta) = R_\theta^{-1}(t)$ with $R_\theta(t) = R_\theta(t-1) + \gamma(t) \left[\psi(t) \Lambda^{-1(t)} \psi^T(t) - R_\theta(t_1) \right]$, $\gamma(t)$ is a step length vector. For the ARMAX, $\psi(t)$ can be sought as follows:

$$\psi(t) = \frac{1}{C(q^{-1})} \phi(t) \quad (10)$$

From the equation (9) and (10), the system parameter, $\hat{\theta}$, can be calculated.

3.2. CONTROL LAW DESIGN

In order to design control law, ARMAX (autoregressive moving average) model of arc/ACLD system is converted into the state space form such that

$$x_{t+1} = Ax_t + Bu_t + Ke_t \quad y_t = Cx_t + e_t \quad (11)$$

where the state estimation error, e_t , is defined as $e_t = x_t - \hat{x}_t$. The steady-state Kalman filter equation is

$$\hat{x}_{t+1} = A\hat{x}_t + Bu_t + K_f \left[y_t - C\hat{x}_t \right] \quad (12)$$

where K_f is the gain of the Kalman filter and y_t is the estimated output measurements. The performance Index of the steady-state system equation should be identified to design control laws by applying optimal control theory. Here, LQR (Linear Quadratic Regulator) controller is applied to obtain the performance Index.

$$J = \frac{1}{2} E \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[x^T(k) Q_w x(k) + u^T(k) R_w u(k) \right] \right] \quad (13)$$

where Q_w is the state-weighting matrix and R_w is the control-weighting matrix. The control gain to minimize the following performance index is

$$k_s = \left[R_w + B^T S_\infty B \right]^{-1} B^T S_\infty A \quad (14)$$

where S_∞ is the solution of Riccati equation as follows:

$$S = A^T SA - A^T SB [B^T SB + R_w]^{-1} B^T SA + Q_w \quad (15)$$

Finally, the optimal control gain can be

$$u_t = -k_s \hat{x}_t \quad (16)$$

4. FEM ANALYSIS

The characteristics of system and mode shapes of specimen are verified by using finite element method. Therefore, Fig 2 shows the mode shapes of specimen. The first mode is a torsion mode at 29.5Hz and the second mode is a bending mode at 46Hz.

Table 1 Natural frequencies of arc type shell model by FEM and experiment

Mode	1 st	2 nd
FREQ (Hz)	29.4(Torsion)	46(Bending)
FEM (Hz)	29	42

Fig. 2 First and second mode shape of Arc type shell model.
 (a) Torsion by FEM (b) Realization of Torsion mode (c) Bending by FEM

5. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION OF ARC/ACLD SYSTEM

5.1 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND PROCEDURES

Figure 3 shows the stacking sequence of a laminated Arc/ACLD system. The host structure is made of Carbon fiber prepreg 3 plies and is mounted in a cantilevered configuration as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3 Stacking sequence of the specimen

The viscoelastic damping polymer of 3M 112 is sandwiched between host structure and piezo actuator layer (PVDF film, MSI, Inc.). Tables 2 and 3 list the main physical and geometrical parameters of the arc host structure, viscoelastic and PVDF film. The inner radius of the curvature of the host structure is 200 mm and its size is 170 (length) × 80 (arc length) mm.

The arc structure is fully covered by the ACLD patch, 170 mm length and 80 mm wide, which consists of a uniformly distributed piezoelectric layer and viscoelastic material.

Table 2 Physical and geometrical properties of the host structure, VEM and PVDF layer

Layer	Thickness (m)	Young's modulus (Pa)	Density (kg/m ³)
Carbon fiber prepreg(*)	125E-5	14.03E10	1800
3M 112 (VEM)	5.08E-5	**	900 - 1000
PVDF	110E-6	2E9	1780

* : 0 degree direction, **: depending on frequency.

Table 3 Main piezoelectric parameters of the PVDF film

d_{31} (m/V)	d_{32} (m/V)	k_{31} (%)	k_t (%)	g_{31} (Vm/N)	g_{32} (Vm/N)
23E-12	3E-12	12	29	216E-3	19E-3

Figure 5 shows a schematic drawing of the experimental set-up used in testing the effectiveness of ACLD treatment in attenuating the vibration of a arc type shell structure. The test structure is excited by an initial displacement condition.

Fig. 4 Specimen shape and boundary condition

The signal from the sensor is amplified through a charge amplifier. The amplified signal is fed to the PC controller to determine the vibration attenuations and to determine control laws through low pass filter and AD converter (PCL 818 Lab. Card). The sensing signal is manipulated, using Linear

Quadratic Regulator (LQR) algorithm, to generate optimal control gains. The control input obtained by LQR controller is sent through DA converter (PCL 818 Lab. Card) to a voltage amplifier through low pass filter. The cutoff frequency of the low pass filter is tuned at 55Hz in order to avoid two conditions. One is to eliminate the electric power noise of 60Hz and the other is not to interfere the target frequency of 46Hz. The amplified control input is fed back to the actuator layer to attenuate the first bending vibration mode of the arc/ACLD system. The voltage range of the sensor signal from the laser sensor of $-5 \sim 5$ V can be sent to the AD converter. Also, the voltage range of the output signal from the DA converter of $-5 \sim 5$ V can be input to the piezo actuator through a voltage amplifier.

Fig.5 Experimental set-up

In order to identify the system parameters of the arc/ACLD system, an experimental method is applied. PRBS (Pseudo Random Binary Sequence) signal, which has infinite discrete frequencies, is used as the actuating signal of the arc/ACLD system. If the frequency of PRBS matches with the natural frequency of the system, the displacement amplitude of the system increases remarkably. Otherwise, the system does not respond well. In this experimental way, the parameters of ARMAX model for the arc/ACLD system can be obtained by comparing the input PRBS signal and output sensor signal. ARMAX model obtained by the system identification is converted into the state space form. Using the state space equation, the gain of Kalman filter could be designed.

5.2 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The vibration amplitudes of an arc structure are shown in Figure 6 when the arc structure is subjected to initial displacement conditions. Figure 6(a) shows the time response of the plain arc, the arc with PCLD (i.e. ACLD is not activated), and the arc with ACLD treatment. And Figure 6(b) shows a comparison between the amplitudes of vibration for the plain arc, the arc/PCLD and the arc/ACLD treatment in frequency domain. From the Figures, the activation of the ACLD treatment has resulted in the effective attenuation of the vibration amplitude of the plain arc structure. In the case of the plain arc structure, the frequency magnitude of the targeted bending mode is 0.014 at about 42Hz. For the PCLD treatment, the frequency magnitude is 0.009 at about 40Hz. Finally, the ACLD system obtained the magnitude of 0.0045 at about 40Hz.

Fig. 6 Time and frequency domain of the plain arc, arc/PCLD, Arc/ACLD treatment.

Figure 7 shows the sensing voltage and control voltage when activated the arc/ACLD system. One thing to be noted here that the attachment of a viscoelastic material to the arc host structure results in shifting the natural frequency of the plain arc structure to the left-hand side. This fact is easily explained by considering the stiffness characteristics of viscoelastic material. On the contrary, applying the control efforts to the arc/ACLD system results in shifting the natural frequency of the arc/ACLD system to the right-hand side. This phenomenon can be understood by considering the stiffness change of a piezo actuator layer due to the control actuations.

Fig. 7 Sensing Voltage and Control Voltage

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented the vibration characteristics of the arc type shell structure with the Active Constrained Layer Damping (ACLD) treatment. To identify the performance of the ACLD treatment, comparisons for the ability of vibration attenuations have been performed between the plain arc, the PCLD treatment, and the ACLD treatment. The system is modeled by using ARMAX and converted into the state-space form in order to design control laws of LQR controller. The ability of the ACLD treatment to attenuate the first bending vibration mode of the arc type shell structure has been successfully demonstrated. Hence, the developed theoretical and experimental techniques developed in this study constitute an invaluable tool for designing of the smart laminated structures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully appreciate the financial support for this research from the Brain Korea 21 Program.

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